

VISOCITY OF AQUEOUS SOLUTIONS CONTAINING AN ELECTROLYTE AND A NON-ELECTROLYTE

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An unsuccessful attempt has been made to find out a mixture law of viscosity for a solution containing an electrolyte and a non-electrolyte. It has been found that the viscosities of mixtures of electrolytes and non-electrolytes can be represented by the equation $\eta/\eta_0 = 1 + A\sqrt{c} + Bc$ but the values of the constants A and B cannot be correlated with the concentration of the non-electrolyte.

The object of the work is to find an expression which would give the viscosity of a mixture containing solutions of an electrolyte and a non-electrolyte whose viscosities and concentrations in the mixture are known separately. For this purpose, succinic acid and calcium chloride have been used as the electrolyte and non-electrolyte, respectively, and the viscosities of the solutions of these two substances and of their mixtures measured by the method described by the authors (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1944, 21, 125), which are accurate within 3 in 10,000.

The results obtained are presented in Table I in which $(\eta/\eta_0 - 1) \times 10^4$ is tabulated instead of the relative viscosity (η/η_0) against the concentrations of succinic acid and calcium chloride in g.mols. per litre. Both η and η_0 refer to 35°.

It has been found that the following relation is obeyed by mixture containing a fixed concentration of succinic acid and different concentrations of calcium chloride

$$\eta/\eta_0 = \eta' + A\sqrt{c} + Bc$$

η' is the relative viscosity of the solution not containing any electrolyte and c is the concentration (in g. mols./litre) of the electrolyte in the mixture. The values of A and B for each set are given at the top of Table I.

The differences between the calculated and observed values of η/η_0 represented as

$$D = [\eta/\eta_0(c) - \eta/\eta_0(o)] \times 10^4$$

have been calculated and are given in Table II which gives an idea of the extent to which the above equation is applicable. It is evident from Table I that the values of A and B change a good deal with a change in the concentration of succinic acid. Further, the value of A is not related to the concentration of succinic acid in any manner; in some cases it has a negative value for which no theoretical explanation can be advanced.

Although no positive contribution to the law governing the viscosity of a solution containing an electrolyte and a non-electrolyte has been made, yet

the experimental data are very accurate and could be employed with advantage by any other worker.

TABLE I

A ...	+0.014	-0.025	+0.015	+0.012	+0.019	+0.032	+0.05	-0.056	+0.000	
B ...	+0.34	+0.58	+0.27	+0.40	+0.34	+0.20	+0.08	+0.78	+0.38	
Hsuc. conc.	0.000	0.001	0.005	0.010	0.015	0.020	0.030	0.050	0.060	0.100
CaCl ₂ conc.										
0.030	0	18	20	23	35	42	59	136	144	224
0.001	7	12	28	30	41	56	79	120	149	—
0.002	13	15	30	34	51	67	82	127	156	—
0.003	18	18	33	42	55	67	87	135	160	—
0.005	27	29	38	44	66	73	96	141	167	—
0.006	31	35	43	48	69	77	101	147	173	—
0.008	40	40	50	68	75	83	109	154	—	—
0.010	48	56	65	73	82	96	114	163	186	—
0.012	56	62	70	87	91	105	123	171	194	—
0.015	69	69	79	102	104	110	130	179	204	—
0.020	88	—	90	110	118	117	149	195	224	—

TABLE II
Values of D

[Hsuc] × 10 ³	1	5	10	15	20	30	50	60
[CaCl ₂]								
0.001	+4	-1	+1	0	-2	-3	+6	+3
0.002	+3	+2	+2	-1	-7	+1	0	0
0.003	+3	+3	0	0	-1	+1	-6	-1
0.005	0	+6	+8	-6	+2	+2	-6	0
0.006	-2	+5	+8	-4	+2	+1	-7	+3
0.008	-1	+5	-2	-1	+4	+1	-6	—
0.010	-5	-3	+2	+4	-2	+3	-5	0
0.012	-2	-4	-3	+5	-4	0	-3	0
0.015	+5	-8	-4	+5	+1	+2	+6	+1
0.020	—	-8	+10	+12	+10	-3	+18	0

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Received April 27, 1946.